

Autoregressive Models with Skewed Innovations

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Abstract

Autoregressive (AR) models are fundamental tools in time series analysis; however, they traditionally assume normally distributed innovations—a condition often violated in real-world applications where data may exhibit skewness. Conventional estimation methods, such as Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and the Yule-Walker Method of Moments, can yield biased and inefficient parameter estimates when applied to time series with non-normal innovations.

In this study, we compare the performance of these conventional methods with the approach proposed by Tiku, Wong, and Bian (2000), which employs Modified Maximum Likelihood (MML) methodology as a robust alternative for AR(q) models with skewed innovations. Both simulation studies and real-world applications are used to evaluate performance.

Through a series of simulations across various conditions—including differing sample sizes, autoregressive coefficients, and shape parameters of a generalized logistic distribution—we assess the bias and efficiency of MML estimators relative to OLS and Yule-Walker estimators. The results consistently demonstrate that MML yields more efficient and less biased estimates, particularly in small-sample settings where the Yule-Walker method often underperforms.

To illustrate its practical utility, the MML method is applied to model daily COVID-19 case counts from Louisiana — a dataset whose innovations exhibit significant deviation from normality. Our analysis shows that the MML methodology provides more accurate estimates of the autoregressive parameter, with substantially smaller standard errors compared to the OLS and Yule-Walker methods. This finding is particularly important in the context of infectious disease modeling, as narrower confidence bands can enable earlier detection of emerging epidemic trends.

We conclude that MMLE offers a superior framework for modeling time series with skewed innovations, delivering more reliable and precise results than conventional approaches.

Key Words: Autoregressive models, Time series, Skewed innovations, Modified Maximum Likelihood Estimation, Robust statistics, COVID-19, Generalized logistic distribution.

1. Introduction

Autoregressive models of order q , AR(q) serve as a cornerstone of time series analysis, with broad applications spanning epidemiology, environmental sciences, and financial modeling. The simplest form of an AR(q) model is the AR (1) model, which uses only the immediate past observation. It is represented as:

$$Y_i = \phi Y_{i-1} + a_i \quad (1)$$

where Y_i is the value of the series at time i , ϕ is the autoregressive coefficient, and a_i is the innovation or error term at time i . A widely adopted assumption in conventional time series modeling has been that these innovations are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.) from a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a constant variance, or $a_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ (Box et al., 2015). This assumption is foundational to estimation methods like Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), traditional Maximum Likelihood (ML), and Yule-Walker Method of Moments Estimation.

However, the assumption of normally distributed innovations is often more a matter of theoretical convenience than an empirical reality. Real-world time series data frequently exhibit characteristics such as skewness, heavy tails, and outliers, all of which violate the normality assumption (Huber & Ronchetti, 2009). When conventional estimation methods are applied under these conditions, the resulting parameter estimates may be inefficient, biased, and ultimately lead to inaccurate forecasts and misleading statistical inferences.

Several studies have explored alternatives to address these limitations. For example, Damsleth and El-Shaarawi (1989) employed a double-exponential (Laplace) distribution in conjunction with iterative ML estimation, while Tan (1985) and Lin (1993) investigated Tiku's (1980) MML approach based on censored normal samples to enhance robustness. Martin and Yohai (1985) examined Huber-type M-estimators for long-tailed symmetric distributions (i.e., those with kurtosis greater than 3). Tiku et al. (1986), on the other hand, demonstrated that such M-estimators are invalid for skewed distributions and inefficient for short-tailed distributions (kurtosis less than 3), limiting their applicability in many real-world scenarios.

The MML method, developed by Tiku (1967, 1968, 1988), provides robust, asymptotically unbiased, and efficient parameter estimates. This methodology was later extended to time series models by Tiku and Suresh (1992), Tiku, Wong, and Bian (1999), Tiku et al. (2000) and Tiku, Wong, & Bian, (2018).

For many non-normal distributions, the corresponding likelihood functions are intractable, often involving nonlinear and complex terms that are difficult to maximize directly. The MML procedure overcomes this challenge by utilizing ordered statistics and applying a Taylor series approximation to linearize the intractable components of the likelihood function. This results in estimators that are both robust and computationally tractable (Islam & Tiku, 2004). These MML estimators have been shown to be asymptotically fully efficient and highly efficient even in small samples (Smith et al., 1973; Lee et al., 1980; Tan, 1985; Schneider, 1986; Bian & Tiku, 1997). In contrast, the efficiency of least squares estimators tends to deteriorate as the distribution departs from normality or as the sample size decreases.

Many previous studies have applied the MML method in the time series context using various innovation distributions. These include the gamma distribution and the generalized logistic distribution (Tiku, Wong, & Bian, 1999), as well as the generalized exponential distribution (Lagos-Álvarez, Ferreira, & Porcu, 2014). Additionally, non-normal symmetric distributions—such as the Student's t-distribution (Tiku, Wong, Vaughan, & Bian, 2000), short-tailed symmetric distributions, and long-tailed symmetric distributions—have also been considered in literature. These studies consistently demonstrated that MML produces estimates with less bias and greater efficiency compared to the least squares method (Bayrak & Akkaya, 2009).

However, despite extensive prior research on MML in time series models, no studies to date have directly compared its performance with classical autoregressive estimation techniques such as the Yule-Walker method. This gap is particularly important given the widespread reliance on traditional estimators in practical applications and popular statistical software, many of which implicitly assume normality of innovations. To address this critical gap, we systematically evaluate the bias and efficiency of MMLE relative to OLS and Yule-Walker estimators across a range of simulation settings that reflect realistic deviations from normality. We then apply these methods to a real-world example from the healthcare domain, where the goal is to estimate the effect of previously reported daily COVID-19 case counts on future case counts and compare the performance of each method.

2.Skewed Innovations

Let the simple AR model of order (1), is as given in equation (1), where the innovations violate the normality assumption of the AR. We use the MML methodology to linearize the intractable terms

in likelihood equations using Taylor's approximation. For simplicity we will only consider the scenario where innovations follow generalized logistic (GL) distribution:

$$a_i \sim f(a; b) = \frac{b}{\sigma} \frac{e^{-\frac{a}{\sigma}}}{\left(1 + e^{-\frac{a}{\sigma}}\right)^{b+1}} \quad (2)$$

Where b is the shape parameter and σ is the scale parameter. Realize that the distribution given in (2) is symmetric when $b=1$ (i.e., the logistic distribution), negatively skewed for $b<1$ and positively skewed for $b>1$ (Figure 1). In this study we assume that b is known.

Figure 1: Generalized logistic distribution probability density function for different values of the shape parameter (b)

The MML estimators for the AR (1) model with GL innovations were derived by Tiku, Wong & Bian (1999) and are presented in equations (3)-(4):

$$\hat{\phi} = K + \hat{\sigma} D \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{\sigma} = \frac{B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4nC}}{2n} \quad (4)$$

where,

$$K = \frac{\sum \beta_i y_{[i]} y_{[i]-1}}{\sum \beta_i y_{[i]-1}^2}, \quad D = \frac{\sum \left(\frac{1}{b+1} - \alpha_i\right) y_{[i]-1}}{\sum \beta_i y_{[i]-1}^2}$$

and

$$B = (b + 1) \sum \left(\frac{1}{b+1} - \alpha_i\right) \{y_{[i]} - K y_{[i]-1}\}, \quad C = (b + 1) \sum \beta_i \{y_{[i]} - K y_{[i]-1}\}^2;$$

see Tiku, Wong & Bian (1999) for details.

3.Simulation Study

To evaluate the performance of the MML method relative to traditional estimators, we conducted a series of Monte Carlo simulations using R software (version 4.3.2, R code is available from the

contact author upon request) under controlled settings that reflect realistic time series scenarios with generalized logistic (GL) innovations. These scenarios included 5000 simulations for each and varied by sample size, the magnitude of the autoregressive coefficient, and the degree of skewness in the innovation distribution, allowing us to assess estimator bias and efficiency across conditions commonly encountered in practice.

Specifically, we compared the performance of MML estimators to conventional time series estimators, namely, OLS and Yule-Walker estimators, under the following different settings:

1. **Autoregressive Coefficient (ϕ):** We considered values of $\phi = -0.5, 0, 0.1, 0.5,$ and 0.9 . These values correspond to negative autocorrelation, no autocorrelation, weak positive autocorrelation, moderate autocorrelation, and strong autocorrelation near the unit root boundary, respectively.
2. **Shape Parameter of the GL Distribution (b):** We examined $b = 0.5, 1, 2, 4,$ and 6 . Values of $b < 1$ correspond to negatively skewed distributions, $b > 1$ to positively skewed distributions, and $b = 1$ to the symmetric logistic distribution.
3. **Sample Size (n):** We assessed performance across three sample sizes: $n = 30$ (small), $n = 250$ (moderate), and $n = 1000$ (large), to explore both small-sample behavior and asymptotic efficiency.

We provide our results in Tables 1-3. To ensure that the data were generated correctly, we also report empirical correlation coefficients $\hat{\rho}$ in Tables 1–3 as a diagnostic measure. Our simulations show that for small sample sizes ($n = 30$), compared to OLS, MML estimators were more accurate and more efficient for all autoregressive coefficients and all values of the shape parameter b . The more popular Yule-Walker method, (known for being computationally efficient under normality assumption) failed to estimate the autoregressive coefficient under all small samples' simulations (Table 1). For larger samples, all methods were asymptotically unbiased, however MML estimators were more efficient compared to other methods. Yule-walker estimators failed to estimate smaller values of autoregression coefficient ($\phi = 0.1$) (Tables 2 and 3).

Overall, our simulation results demonstrate that MML estimation outperforms both OLS and Yule-Walker estimators, particularly in small sample settings with non-normal innovations. MML consistently provides more accurate and efficient estimates across all conditions, while the Yule-Walker method exhibits substantial failure in estimating autoregressive parameter ϕ under small samples and low autocorrelation scenarios. Although all methods are asymptotically unbiased in large samples, MML retained superior efficiency, highlighting its practical advantage in finite-sample applications. While not shown here, similar improvements were also observed in the estimation of the scale parameter σ .

Table 2: Simulation of different estimation method for autoregressive coefficient when sample size is 250. ϕ is the autoregressive parameter, $\hat{\phi}_{MML}$ is the estimator under MML, $\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$ is the OLS estimator, $\hat{\phi}_{YW}$ is Yule-Walker estimator and $\hat{\rho}$ is the autocorrelation for lag 1.

$n = 250$	$\phi = -0.5$			$\phi = 0$			$\phi = 0.1$			$\phi = 0.5$			$\phi = 0.9$		
	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE
	$b = 0.5$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4963258			0.003263054			0.09549811			0.4911531			0.8908606		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4963873	1.305139e-05	0.002166201	0.0005501529	3.026682e-07	0.002396808	0.0999185	6.642822e-09	0.002261613	0.4979792	4.083813e-06	0.001265237	0.8908606	1.873853e-06	0.0001019349
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4971522	8.110043e-06	0.003032443	-0.003261944	1.064028e-05	0.004021724	0.09546242	2.05896e-05	0.003991467	0.4903216	9.367197e-05	0.003160338	0.8853069	0.0002158874	0.001136367
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4952169	2.287761e-05	0.003037343	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	-0.4952169	2.287761e-05	0.003037343	0.8813325	0.0003484745	0.00129519
	$b = 1$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4964561			-0.003499185			0.0952614			0.4909446			0.885839		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4957423	1.812779e-05	0.002787252	0.0004623427	2.137608e-07	0.003635032	0.0996872	9.784557e-08	0.003596964	0.4966447	1.125831e-05	0.002771849	0.8934303	4.316109e-05	0.0008353155
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4973022	7.278126e-06	0.002999986	-0.003497201	1.223041e-05	0.003998899	0.09522669	2.27845e-05	0.003978399	0.4901412	9.719588e-05	0.003176019	0.8846977	0.0002341602	0.001187471
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4953616	2.151467e-05	0.003003509	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4880312	0.000143253	0.003219244	0.8806432	0.0003746843	0.001352139
	$b = 2$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4966322			-0.003692963			0.09507414			0.4908954			0.8934724		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4965742	1.173582e-05	0.002311486	-0.0002092563	4.378819e-08	0.002439504	0.09917924	6.736487e-07	0.002267503	0.4975617	5.945507e-06	0.001187528	0.8934724	1.691417e-06	8.699932e-05
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4974636	6.433342e-06	0.002981597	-0.003691237	1.362523e-05	0.003978736	0.09503851	2.461641e-05	0.003960376	0.4900212	9.957688e-05	0.00316279	0.8859063	0.0001986315	0.001066285
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4955187	2.008182e-05	0.002985343	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4878953	0.0001465242	0.003208321	0.8818511	0.0003293831	0.001235918
	$b = 4$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4967936			-0.003807139			0.09496539			0.4910176			0.9109736		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4966695	1.109233e-05	0.001687214	0.001044251	1.09046e-06	0.001420394	0.1006965	4.850927e-07	0.001254273	0.499818	3.313571e-08	0.0005180549	0.8998205	3.222059e-08	2.701932e-05
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4975681	5.914124e-06	0.002972614	-0.003805902	1.448489e-05	0.003966622	0.0949285	2.572008e-05	0.0039479	0.4899589	0.0001008241	0.00314592	0.888357	0.0001355592	0.0008474273
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4956214	1.917202e-05	0.002977442	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4878206	0.0001483378	0.003196177	0.8845004	0.000240237	0.00101041
	$b = 6$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4968797			-0.003846275			0.09492831			0.4911526			0.9219874		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.496264	1.395741e-05	0.00149792	0.001858082	3.452467e-06	0.001192603	0.1015239	2.322123e-06	0.001041782	0.5004942	2.442651e-07	0.0004119608	0.8999936	4.068351e-11	2.04393e-05
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4976044	5.739041e-06	0.002969367	-0.003845262	1.478604e-05	0.00396234	0.09489085	2.610339e-05	0.00394327	0.4899411	0.0001011816	0.003137682	0.8898444	0.000103137	0.0007212524
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4956573	1.885887e-05	0.002974985	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4877956	0.0001489465	0.003191032	0.8861932	0.0001906264	0.0008743263

Table 3: Simulation of different estimation method for autoregressive coefficient when sample size is 1000. ϕ is the autoregressive parameter, $\hat{\phi}_{MML}$ is the estimator under MML, $\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$ is the OLS estimator, $\hat{\phi}_{YW}$ is Yule-Walker estimator and $\hat{\rho}$ is the autocorrelation for lag 1.

$n = 1000$	$\phi = -0.5$			$\phi = 0$			$\phi = 0.1$			$\phi = 0.5$			$\phi = 0.9$		
	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE	Mean	Bias ²	MSE
	$b = 0.5$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4989087			-0.0008761303			0.0987824			0.4976767			0.8977604		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4987695	1.514042e-06	0.000525199	0.0002159682	4.664225e-08	0.0005849543	0.100019	3.622884e-10	0.0005508592	0.4994587	2.929565e-07	0.0003043013	0.8996553	1.188489e-07	2.293968e-05
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4991185	7.770004e-07	0.0007445911	-0.0008769772	7.69089e-07	0.0009833014	0.09877085	1.510808e-06	0.0009741266	0.4974468	6.518617e-06	0.0007581835	0.8962408	1.413187e-05	0.0002129465
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4986223	1.898123e-06	0.0007451628	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4969567	9.261816e-06	0.0007618169	0.8953199	2.190369e-05	0.0002219862
	$b = 1$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4989717			-0.001024297			0.0986231			0.4975043			0.8964559		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4987228	1.631162e-06	0.0006892059	3.010499e-05	9.063105e-10	0.0009038857	0.09979213	4.320806e-08	0.000895023	0.4989516	1.09905e-06	0.0006911762	0.8982076	3.2128e-06	0.0001829976
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4991854	6.635488e-07	0.0007456493	-0.00102484	1.050297e-06	0.0009894596	0.09861178	1.927164e-06	0.0009822678	0.4972834	7.379962e-06	0.0007685202	0.896104	1.517862e-05	0.0002178723
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4986867	1.724667e-06	0.000745975	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4967928	1.028635e-05	0.0007715893	0.895188	2.315524e-05	0.0002267195
	$b = 2$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4990312			-0.001123384			0.09851773			0.4974149			0.8982571		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4990673	8.698859e-07	0.000580992	-0.0001636713	2.678831e-08	0.0006220773	0.09967198	1.075954e-07	0.0005802477	0.4993188	4.640641e-07	0.000303044	0.8996881	9.728993e-08	1.968806e-05
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4992408	5.763782e-07	0.0007499225	-0.001123799	1.262925e-06	0.0009951699	0.09850639	2.230869e-06	0.0009883925	0.4971785	7.960616e-06	0.0007728358	0.8961553	1.478177e-05	0.0002121712
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4987395	1.588888e-06	0.0007504117	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4966882	1.096786e-05	0.0007755185	0.8952465	2.259556e-05	0.0002218522
	$b = 4$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4990785			-0.00117338			0.09846495			0.4974077			0.9033423		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4991671	6.937593e-07	0.0004227029	0.0001844255	3.401276e-08	0.0003578678	0.1001025	1.050938e-08	0.0003167378	0.499939	3.720363e-09	0.0001304411	0.8999623	1.419534e-09	6.387424e-06
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4992738	5.273997e-07	0.0007534414	-0.001173757	1.377704e-06	0.0009986915	0.09845353	2.391564e-06	0.0009917587	0.497127	8.254331e-06	0.0007738888	0.8963784	1.311592e-05	0.000197135
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.4987704	1.511819e-06	0.0007541246	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4966377	1.13048e-05	0.0007763788	0.8954814	2.041741e-05	0.0002083661
	$b = 6$														
$\hat{\rho}$	-0.4991024			-0.001189229			0.09844827			0.4974289			0.9072894		
$\hat{\phi}_{MML}$	-0.4990867	8.340264e-07	0.0003731829	0.0003951266	1.56125e-07	0.0002983292	0.1003186	1.015001e-07	0.0002612554	0.500113	1.277704e-08	0.0001033033	0.9000059	3.531916e-11	4.878404e-06
$\hat{\phi}_{OLS}$	-0.4992853	5.107692e-07	0.0007547832	-0.001189596	1.41514e-06	0.0009999178	0.09843681	2.443551e-06	0.0009928732	0.4971108	8.34771e-06	0.0007739883	0.8965515	1.189217e-05	0.0001863357
$\hat{\phi}_{YW}$	-0.498781	1.48598e-06	0.000755552	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.4966223	1.140882e-05	0.0007764232	0.8956653	1.878923e-05	0.0001984863

4. Application: COVID-19 Data

Accurately estimating infectious disease case numbers in advance is critical for ensuring that healthcare systems are adequately prepared, helping to prevent overload and ensuring the availability of essential resources such as hospital beds and medical supplies. Early projections enable public health authorities to implement timely interventions—such as lockdowns, social distancing measures, and targeted testing—and inform key policy decisions related to vaccine distribution, travel restrictions, and emergency response planning. Reliable forecasts also influence public behavior by encouraging individuals to take appropriate precautions, while providing researchers with valuable data to evaluate the effectiveness of intervention strategies. In addition, these estimates support economic planning by helping manage supply chains and mitigate potential disruptions. Overall, early case forecasting enhances the ability to manage and reduce the societal impact of infectious disease outbreaks (Mohamed et al., 2025).

Time-series data generated during pandemics—such as daily new case counts or hospitalizations—are typically highly volatile and often exhibit non-normal features, including skewness, heavy tails, and outliers. These characteristics violate key assumptions of traditional time series models and can significantly impair the performance of conventional estimation methods.

In this study, we investigate an AR(1) model to characterize the background infection rate of daily COVID-19 cases in the state of Louisiana (USA), using data from the *New York Times* spanning the period from Feb 01 to June 30, 2021—a time when no epidemic surge was observed and the assumption of stationarity (or trend stationarity) is reasonable (see Figure 2).

In our analysis, we applied a 7-day moving average to account for weekly reporting variation, specifically the underreporting that typically occurs on weekends due to administrative delays. We detrended our dataset to remove the general trend and achieve stationarity (Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test = -5.2289, p-value = 0.01; Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin test = 0.42945, p-value = 0.06446), then we checked the autocorrelation function and the partial autocorrelation function of the time-series variable “new daily cases”. As in Figure 3, our data show that the partial autocorrelation function is significant at lag one, while the autocorrelation function is fading down gradually, indicating first order autoregressive model AR (1) (Shumway, R. H., & Stoffer, D. S., 2017). We then checked whether AR (1) model innovations are normally distributed using normal-probability plot (Figure 4) which showed deviation from normality at the tails (Shapiro-Wilk normality test = 0.93675, p-value = 3.233e-06).

To apply the MML method, we estimated the shape parameter by comparing likelihood values across several candidate shape parameter values, and provided them in Table 4; see Oral and Kadilar (2011) and Oral and Danos (2018). The likelihood function peaks near $b = 3$; accordingly, we assume GL with $b = 3$ for the innovation distribution. Then we compared the three estimation methods to the detrended data and provided our results in Table 5. As can be seen from Table 5, all methods provided similar values for the autoregression coefficient $\hat{\phi}$, however the MML method had the least standard error compared to OLS and Yule-Walker method of moments.

Table 4: Estimating the shape parameter (b) through the log likelihood values

b	0.5	1	2	3	4	5
$\text{Ln } L$	40.77	146.44	254.32	272.03	248.49	203.19

Table 5: Comparison of estimation methods for the autoregressive coefficient of detrended COVID-19 data in Louisiana during April 15th – June 30th, 2021

Method	Estimate ($\hat{\phi}$)	Standard Error
Modified Maximum Likelihood	0.92775	0.00005
Ordinary Least Squares	0.89650	0.01893
Yule-Walker Method of Moments	0.89114	0.00140

Figure 2: Daily new cases of Covid-19 in the State of Louisiana (USA) as reported by the New York Times Journal.

Figure 3: Autocorrelation (ACF, left) and Partial Autocorrelation (Partial ACF, right)

Figure 4: Histogram (left) and normal-probability plot (right) of the innovations of AR(1) model.

4. Discussion

This study highlights the critical importance of addressing non-normality in time series modeling, particularly in AR frameworks applied to real-world data. Traditional methods such as OLS and Yule-Walker estimators rely heavily on the assumption of normally distributed innovations—an assumption that is frequently violated in practice, especially in epidemiological and environmental time series, where data often exhibit skewness, heavy tails, and outliers.

Through extensive simulations, we demonstrate that the MML method outperforms conventional estimators in both accuracy and efficiency under non-normal innovations. These advantages are especially pronounced in small-sample scenarios, where classical estimators often break down or yield highly variable results. Furthermore, our application to daily COVID-19 case data in Louisiana illustrates that MML provides more reliable parameter estimates during periods of baseline transmission, which is essential for early detection of emerging epidemic trends.

These findings underscore the necessity of adopting estimation techniques that are robust to departures from normality when modeling real-world time series. Blind adherence to the Gaussian assumption not only risks biased inference but can also delay critical public health decisions in time-sensitive contexts. As such, MML offers a compelling alternative for practitioners seeking more dependable modeling of time-dependent processes with complex error structures.

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